

SIMULTANEOUS MULTI-FREQUENCY DIELECTRIC ANALYSIS OF THE POLYMERIZATION OF ANIONIC POLYAMIDE 6

Maximilian Eberhardt – Fraunhofer IGCV

Thermoplastic Resin-Transfer-Molding (T-RTM)

- T-RTM offers several advantages compared to similar manufacturing techniques
 - Low viscosity melt
 - High degree of crystallization
 - Long molecular chains
 - Superior quality of manufactured parts
- Process control is challenging
- Very susceptible to external influences
- No measurement of in-mold parameters possible so far

Dielectric Measurement System DEA+

- Innovative approach for time synchronous acquisition of multiple frequency components
- Wide measurement bandwidth: 10^2 Hz to 10^7 Hz
- Up to 50 full measurements per second
- Online monitoring of curing processes and real time characterization of material samples possible
- Other fields of application
 - Determination of mixture ratios
 - Cure monitoring of highly dynamic systems (e.g. UV light activated adhesives)
 - Contamination control of oils and lubricants

Measurement Data

- 3D representation of results offers new possibilities of process monitoring and control
- Multiple dielectric parameters can be accessed to achieve a detailed interpretation of the measured data

Cure Monitoring

- New measurement system allows a more detailed analysis than the entirely reactive temperature method and conventional DEA
- Separation of the polymerization has not been observed before and is being investigated
- In-mold application is possible offering new process control possibilities

